

Vineyard control and monitoring

I. Scenario Description

A groupware system is available to support agricultural technicians and operators in vineyard management tasks. The technicians walk through the vineyard with their drones to inspect each of the vines and take parameters such as temperature and humidity, to record the state of each plant, and to take photographs of the branches and leaves as well as the fruit depending on the season. Computer vision algorithms are used to detect possible diseases and necessary actions on the vines. In this case, messages will be sent to the operators under the supervision of the technicians to carry out sanitary treatment, pruning or other functions; this task programming will be recorded in the system.

The oenologists and the manager have access to a representation of the vineyard in the form of a digital twin, with which they monitor the vineyard. They can communicate with each other via video conference and chat. In addition to the parameters recorded and the actions programmed and carried out on each vine, the digital twin also integrates general climatic information of the vineyard historically through a collection of sensors distributed throughout the plantation (temperature, wind, humidity, sunlight...), and obtains accurate weather forecast data from external services. By analysing all the information available, the manager can issue alerts to all the workers regarding the start of the harvest and the vineyard's preparation for a storm or frost.

Scenario 1

The exploration of the vineyard by the technicians, which generates orders in real time for the operators and a representation of the tasks to be performed on a map view of the vineyard.

Scenario 2

The monitoring by the manager of the activity of the technicians and operators through their location on the vineyard map and the type of work they carry out (inspection, sanitary treatment, pruning, etc.), represented by a visual signal of a specific colour. Both the technicians and operators use the system via a smart phone with a GPS, although the technicians also carry a drone.

II. Awareness Description Diagrams

References

Duque, R., Bravo, C., Bringas, S., Postigo, D. (2023) [Leveraging a visual language for the awareness-based design of interaction requirements in digital twins](#). Future Generation Computer Systems, 153, pp. 41-51